

Marine ecosystem classification for near seabed waters of Europe

Deliverable 2.4

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How to Cite

Campoy, A.N., Assis, J., Addamo, A.M., Zhao, Q., Costello M.J. 2023. Marine ecosystem classification for near seabed waters of Europe. Nord University, *MPA Europe Project Report Deliverable 2.4*, 19 pp. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.10421632>

Co-funded by
the European Union

UK Research
and Innovation

MPA Europe is co-funded by the European Union under the Horizon Europe programme (Grant Agreement: 101059988). UK participants in Horizon Europe Project MPA Europe are supported by UKRI grant numbers 10067934 JNCC and 10069750 SAMS.

Views and opinions expressed are those of the authors only and do not necessarily reflect that of the European Union or UK Research and Innovation. Neither the European Union nor the granting authority can be held responsible for them.

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The MPA Europe project

MPA Europe is a project co-funded by the European Union (EU) that will map a network of locations representative of biodiversity in European seas (Atlantic Exclusive Economic Zones of the EU and its neighbours, and all the Mediterranean, Baltic, and Black seas) (Figure A).

Figure A. MPA Europe study area.

This network will indicate where to prioritise placement of Marine Protected Areas (MPA) for biodiversity protection and how Maritime Spatial Planning (MSP) can maximise blue carbon benefits. By using a holistic set of biodiversity measures, from species to ecosystems (including habitats), and environmental data including carbon storage, water currents, and climate change velocity models, it will be possible to quantify and map both the present and future connectivity within the proposed MPA network. The multiple scenarios provided will support wider and improved MSP by policy makers, industry, and non-governmental organizations (NGOs). The major scientific areas of the project and its outcomes are summarized in the infographic presented in Figure B.

Figure B. MPA Europe project scientific areas

The inter-disciplinary approach of MPA Europe is supported by a diversity of partners. These include Nord University (Norway), the Intergovernmental Oceanographic Commission of UNESCO (Belgium), Aarhus University (Denmark), Climazul (Greece), the Centre of Marine Sciences (Portugal), Science Crunchers (Portugal), the Joint Nature Conservation Committee (England, UK), the Scottish Association for Marine Science (Scotland, UK), the Ocean University of China (China), and the University of the Ryukyus (Japan). The partners include experts in marine biology, taxonomy, ecology, oceanography, biogeochemistry, and biogeography, MPA network design, benthic habitat mapping, carbon dynamics, species distribution, climate modelling, and MSP compose the MPA Europe team.

Deliverable 2.4 overview

The present document details the data acquisition and computational procedures involved in Deliverable 2.4 of MPA Europe. It provides the **classification of marine ecosystems in Europe for near seabed waters** driven by a wide range of spatially complete and standardised environmental data that reflect both ecosystem conditions and functioning.

The classification of ecosystems considered clustering algorithms fitting high-resolution environmental data for European seas (Environmental data preparation; Deliverable 2.1, WP2; Assis et al, 2023). In this scope and for the purposes of the MPA Europe project, ‘ecosystems’ are defined as ***“enduring, spatially bounded environments where biological and energy interactions are greater within than with other ecosystems”*** (Zhao *et al.* 2019). The information provided is crucial for policy-relevant research focusing on MPA designation, in particular, mapping biodiversity patterns. It will feed the main subsequent tasks of Prioritisation (WP5), which aim to design (prioritise locations for) MPA networks using a systematic conservation planning approach maximising the coverage of the marine biodiversity.

Methods

The environmental data used in cluster analysis was derived from Deliverable 2.1 (WP2, Assis et al., 2023). These data comprise high-resolution (0.05 degrees, approx. 5 km at the equator), spatially complete and standardised environmental data layers for the European seas, generated with information from the Global Ocean Physics Analysis and Forecast and the Global Ocean Biogeochemistry Analysis and Forecast, two pre-processed re-analyses of Copernicus Marine Service that integrate and assimilate a comprehensive range of satellite and in-situ data (Assis et al., 2023).

Ten meaningful environmental variables for the near seabed waters of European seas were selected. Seven of them were also used for surface waters (Deliverable 2.3), namely, dissolved molecular oxygen (mmol m^{-3}), nitrate (mmol m^{-3}), ocean temperature ($^{\circ}\text{C}$), pH, phosphate (mmol m^{-3}), phytoplankton (mmol m^{-3}), and salinity. Sea ice cover (%) is the only variable excluded for near seabed waters. Additional topographic variables, namely, slope (expressing depth changes over distance), terrain ruggedness index (expressing depth changes between adjacent focal cells) and topographic position index (comparing the depth of focal cells to the mean elevation of adjacent focal cells) were included. Data were represented as the averaged values over the decade 2010-2020. Thus, the ecosystem classification reflects the long-term enduring “climatology” that drives the distribution of species and habitats as distinct from seasonal and annual variation that affect population abundance. The correlation among selected variables was assessed through the Pearson's correlation coefficient (Table 1).

Data were standardised using Z-scores. This procedure involved adjusting each data point to be centred on the mean and scaled based on the standard deviation. Standardisation with Z-scores is crucial for removing scale bias, ensuring an unbiased interpretation of results, and facilitating comparisons between variables.

*Table 1. Pearson's correlation coefficient for the ten environmental variables selected: dissolved molecular oxygen, nitrate, ocean temperature (temp.), pH, phosphate (phosp.), salinity, slope, terrain ruggedness index (rugg.), topographic position index (topog.) and phytoplankton (phyto). Absolute correlation values higher than 0.70 (Dormann et al. 2013) are highlighted in **bold**.*

	Oxygen	Nitrate	Temp.	pH	Phosp.	Salinity	Slope	Rugg.	Topog.	Phyto.
Oxygen	1	0.19	-0.60	-0.35	-0.55	-0.17	-0.15	-0.21	0.01	0.17
Nitrate		1	-0.63	-0.54	0.06	0.26	0.20	0.19	-0.03	-0.47
Temp.			1	0.31	-0.16	0.10	-0.01	0.07	0.02	0.32
pH				1	0.30	0.20	-0.02	-0.03	0.03	0.09
Phosp.					1	-0.28	0.04	0.04	-0.02	-0.19
Salinity						1	0.14	0.15	0.00	-0.35
Slope							1	0.93	0.01	-0.17
Rugg.								1	0.04	-0.17
Topog.									1	0.01
Phyto.										1

*Table 2. Result of the Principal Component Analysis (PCA). The first six principal components (PC1-6) recovered 93 % of the variance in the data matrix (in **bold**).*

	PC1	PC2	PC3	PC4	PC5	PC6	PC7	PC8	PC9	PC10
Standard deviation	1.58	1.51	1.22	1.13	0.99	0.88	0.67	0.32	0.24	0.16
Proportion of variance	0.24	0.22	0.15	0.12	0.09	0.07	0.04	0.01	0.00	0.00
Cumulative proportion	0.24	0.47	0.62	0.75	0.85	0.93	0.98	0.99	0.99	1

Principal Component Analysis (PCA) was further performed to mitigate inter-variable correlations and reduce data dimensionality. PCA is a multivariate technique that transforms the original variables into a new set of orthogonal variable dimensions called principal components. The initial six principal components were selected, which collectively explained 93 % of the variance (Table 2). By retaining these components, information was effectively captured while reducing the complexity of the dataset.

The PCA led to a data matrix comprising 658,034 rows (i.e., linked to the 0.05 resolution cells) and six columns. The dataset underwent normalization by scaling each variable to a range between 0 and 1 (Figure 1). This preprocessing step ensured that variables with different scales contributed equally to subsequent analyses. By eliminating the influence of variable scales, the normalized data provides a foundation for accurate and meaningful interpretations, especially when employing algorithms sensitive to input feature magnitudes, such as clustering and distance-based methods.

Figure 1. Variable distribution in the dataset before clustering. Each of the six variables corresponds to a principal component (PC1-6) preserved after PCA.

K-means clustering approach was utilised to find structure in the data. This is a popular unsupervised machine learning algorithm used for partitioning a dataset into a predefined number of distinct, non-overlapping clusters. It works by iteratively assigning data points to the nearest cluster centroid and then recalculating the centroids based on the mean of the points assigned to each cluster. This process continues until convergence, when the centroids no longer change significantly. K-means algorithms seek to minimise the within-cluster sum of squared (WCSS) distances, i.e., between data points and the centroids of their respective clusters. Thus, it is suitable for clustering data points with numerical features into K clusters, where K is a user-specified parameter. It is an efficient method known for its simplicity in cluster assignment.

The appropriate number of clusters was determined using the library *NbClust* (Charrad *et al.* 2014) of R computing language (R Core Team, 2023). It implements and compares 30 cluster validity

indices to provide the best clustering structure consensus from a range of results. Due to the substantial size of the dataset and the *NbClust* requirement to compute a distance matrix, resource limitation prevented from executing the function for the entire dataset. Instead, 100 random samples of a size of 10,000 were iteratively generated to calculate the validity indices. A dissimilarity matrix was computed for each subset using Euclidean distances to test a up to 20 possible clusters. The outcome derived from the combination of indices indicated that three clusters is the optimal choice to structure the data (Figure 2).

Figure 2. Optimal number of clusters according to the combined outcome of 30 cluster validity indices obtained from 100 random samples of 10,000 data points. $K=3$ was selected more often (Count) across indices and samples.

K-means clustering was then applied to the data using the *kmeans* function in R with a fixed number of clusters equal to three, as previously estimated, while considering the Lloyd’s algorithm and a maximum of 100 iterations. Lloyd’s algorithm is a three-step approach to minimize the within-cluster sum of squared distances. In our case, this algorithm starts by choosing three random data points as centroids (previously estimated $k = 3$). Then, it assigns all data points to their closest centroid, and finally it performs the recalculation of centroids as mean over all their assigned data points. These last two steps are repeated until the defined maximum of 100 iterations. Since the resulting clusters are heavily influenced by the choosing of initial centroids, i.e., the Lloyd’s algorithm might get stuck in a local optimum, we allowed for 25 random initial centroid assignments.

Further, within the K-means method, uncertainty in the cluster assignments was estimated by incorporating fuzzy logic approach, which assigns data points to clusters based on degrees of membership. This means that data points can belong to multiple clusters with varying degrees of likelihood, allowing for the representation of uncertainty and overlapping patterns.

The Euclidean distance between clusters was calculated as the mean of all pairwise distances among the data points from different clusters. The resulting distance matrix was utilized to construct a dendrogram illustrating the hierarchical grouping of individual elements into clusters based on their relative Euclidean distances. This was achieved using the R function *hclust*, which performs agglomerative hierarchical clustering.

The clustering quality and statistical significance was inferred through four independent indices: Average Jaccard Index, Cluster Instability, Dunn Index, and Silhouette Score. These metrics, which are described in detail in Table 3, capture different aspects of cluster quality, providing a more holistic understanding of the resulting structure. Significance of indices was assessed through bootstrapping, by comparing the validation scores of the actual clustering to the distribution of scores obtained from 1,000 randomizations. This approach determines the proportion of random validation scores that are equal to or greater than the actual validation scores. A significance level of $\alpha = 0.05$ was used to determine statistical significance.

Table 3. Summary of clustering validation metrics.

Metrics	Description
Average Jaccard Index	It measures the similarity between all pairs of clusters and then computes the average. It ranges from 0 to 1. Higher values indicate better-defined clusters, with 1 implying perfect cluster similarity.
Cluster Instability	It quantifies the cluster assignment sensitivity to slight changes in the data. It ranges from 0 to 1, with 0 indicating perfect stability and 1 indicating complete instability.
Dunn Index	It is the ratio of the minimum inter-cluster distance to the maximum intra-cluster distance. It theoretically ranges from 0 to infinity, however, values from 0 to 1 are more common. A higher value suggests better clustering, where clusters are more compact and well-separated from each other.
Silhouette Score	It measures how similar an object is to its own cluster (intra-cluster similarity) compared to other clusters (inter-cluster dissimilarity). It provides a way to quantify the separation between clusters and the cohesion within clusters. It ranges from -1 to +1, where -1 implies incorrect clustering, 0 suggests overlapping clusters, and 1 indicates well-defined and well-separated clusters.

Results

Three clusters were identified among the near seabed waters of European seas, with sizes (in decreasing order) of 413,557 cells (~63 % area, cluster 1), 198,421 cells (~30 %, cluster 2), and 46,056 cells (7 %, cluster 3), at a resolution of 0.05 degrees.

The spatial distribution of the clusters was well-resolved. In detail, **cluster 1** defined the Arctic Sea and most of the deep offshore Northeast Atlantic Ocean. **Cluster 2** defined most of the Mediterranean Sea and the Northeast Atlantic continental shelf from Morocco to Norway, plus the Faeroe Islands and southern Iceland. Cluster 2 is absent from Jan Mayen, Svalbard and surrounding smaller islands in the Arctic. **Cluster 3** defined the Baltic and Black Seas together with small coastal zones off North France, Belgium, Netherlands, Germany and Denmark (Figure 3).

Figure 3. European marine ecosystems of near seabed waters estimated by k-means clustering analysis of environmental data. Data aggregated into equal-area hexagons 10 km wide for representation. Colour scale defines the three distinctive clusters identified in this study.

Fuzzy logic analysis based on k-means clustering showed very high assignment precision to a single cluster. In a range of membership values between 0 (i.e., fuzzy assignment) and 1 (i.e., clear assignment), the precision varied from 0.33 to 1, with a median of 0.74 across the European seas (Figure 4). Despite the overall patterns, lower precision cells were mainly associated in contact zones between clusters (Figure 4). These areas may represent intermediate environmental conditions shared among adjacent ecosystems.

Figure 4. Clustering assignment precision based on fuzzy logic, where 1 is most precise. Values range from 0.33 to 1 and define the precision of each cells' assignment to the respective cluster.

Hierarchical clustering analysis based on environmental distance between clusters showed distinctive cluster relationships (Figure 5). It revealed that clusters 1 and 2 are more closely related than cluster 3, which exhibited the greatest distinctiveness for its environmental uniqueness. Clusters 1 and 2 differed with a relative distance of 0.75.

The resultant WCSS, a measure of the variability or dispersion of data points within each cluster, was: $WCSS_1 = 5,454.98$; $WCSS_2 = 2,498.42$; and $WCSS_3 = 4,681.65$ for clusters 1-3, respectively. The R^2 (i.e., proportion of the total variation explained by the clustering) was 43.7 %. Regarding the cluster validation, Dunn Index and Silhouette Score significant values of 0.54 and 0.34 respectively (Table 4), revealed a high-quality data structuring, with compact and well-defined clusters. In

addition, at the cluster level, low Cluster Instability of 0.15 were retrieved, reinforcing that clusters are well-separated, non-overlapping and distinct from each other.

Figure 5. Environmental Euclidean distance between clusters.

Table 4. Results of clustering validation metrics.

	Cluster Instability	Dunn Index	Silhouette Score
Clustering validation	0.15	0.54	0.34

Environmental variables more correlated with other variables (temperature, terrain ruggedness index and slope; Table 1) contributed less unique information to the PCA. On the contrary, topographic position index and phytoplankton were the higher contributors. However, it is important to note that all values exceeded 90 %, indicating that all variables contributed to the principal components in a very similar proportion (Figure 6).

Figure 6. Percentage of variance explained by the Principal Component Analysis after excluding each environmental variable: topographic position index (topog.), phytoplankton (phyto), salinity, pH, nitrate, phosphate (phosp.), dissolved molecular oxygen (oxygen), ocean temperature (temp.), slope, and terrain ruggedness index (rugg.).

The clusters were well-resolved and linked to distinct environmental characteristics (Figure 7; Table 5). A cold temperature, depth (topographic position), and higher slope distinguished the deep offshore cluster 1. Warmer temperature distinguished the continental shelf cluster 2, and low salinity distinguished cluster 3.

Figure 7. Environmental characteristics of the five identified clusters. Variables: dissolved molecular oxygen, nitrate, ocean temperature (temp), pH, phosphate, salinity, slope, terrain ruggedness index (rugg), topographic position index (topog.), and phytoplankton (phyto). Mean of each variable in red and range (minimum and maximum) in yellow. It is important to note that the values are presented in percentages, where 0-100 % represents the full range of each variable. This approach ensures comparability among the clusters.

Table 5. Summary of the environmental characteristics of the five identified clusters. Variables: dissolved molecular oxygen (oxygen), nitrate, ocean temperature (temp), pH, phosphate, salinity, slope, terrain ruggedness index (rugg), topographic position index (topog.), and phytoplankton (phyto). Mean of each variable and range [min, max]. Distinguishing variables are in red.

	Oxygen (mmol m-3)	Nitrate (mmol m-3)	Temp. (°C)	pH	Phosphate (mmol m-3)	Salinity	Slope	Rugg	Topog	Phyto. (mmol m-3)
Cluster 1	280 [59, 373]	15.1 [0.01, 30.5]	1.75 [-1.36, 20.3]	7.99 [7.77, 8.27]	1.05 [0.01, 5.32]	35 [22.6, 39.2]	1.08 [0, 18.2]	68.4 [0, 1000]	-2.31 [-1000, 787]	0.03 [0.01, 1.35]
Cluster 2	222 [0.71, 316]	6.64 [0.00, 28.8]	11.9 [5.33, 23.7]	8.03 [7.8, 8.37]	0.43 [0.00, 7.26]	36.8 [26.5, 39.8]	0.71 [0.00, 9.19]	54.3 [0.08, 1076]	1.05 [-566, 1076]	0.29 [0.01, 4.12]
Cluster 3	226 [0.23, 409]	2.39 [0, 31.2]	7.63 [-0.95, 21.5]	8.02 [7.2, 8.38]	2.9 [8.73, 0.01]	15 [1.87, 39.1]	0.57 [0.00, 22]	40.7 [0.10, 2466]	1.31 [-519, 2466]	0.87 [0.01, 12.9]

Cluster analysis depends on the choice of environmental variables, distance measures and clustering methods (or algorithms). Therefore, we have explored additional metrics and criteria to map ecosystems (see Appendix 1). We added mean depth to the list of initial ten meaningful environmental variables for the near seabed waters. Three evaluation methods (i.e. Silhouette, Calinski-Harabasz and Davies-Bouldin) were used to assess the number of clusters yielding results with a higher number of marine ecosystems, i.e., k=9 (Figure S2a), K=13 (Figure S2b) and K=18 (Figure S2c) that were obtained with the alternative distance functions Euclidean distance and cosine similarity, and clustering methods (i.e., kmeans and Gaussian Mixture Models (GMMs)) (Table S1) (see Appendix 1 for further details on methodology and results). The different number of clusters show how relevant are the criteria used for selection of both the environmental variable significant

for the scope of the analysis, and the combination of distance measures and clustering methods. The complexity of marine ecosystems might be reflected and resolved using hierarchical clustering methods, which are underway. In addition, we will explore the effect of excluding seabed variables (ruggedness, depth, slope, topographic position) from the classification. This may be particularly helpful for comparing and perhaps integrating the present near seabed, and previous surface, ecosystem classifications; which is next step in the MPA Europe ecosystem classification.

In summary, through selection of biologically meaningfully environmental variables, and the application of K-means clustering analysis, the current deliverable provides a robust classification of marine ecosystems in European near seabed waters that reflect both ecosystem conditions and functioning. This reveals three well-defined clusters, each associated with distinct environmental characteristics. These clusters provide valuable insights for policymakers and researchers, particularly in the context of marine protected area designation and biodiversity conservation. The rigorous validation metrics demonstrate the quality and reliability of the clustering results, reinforcing their significance for the MPA Europe project's objectives.

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Appendix

Appendix 1. Exploring additional metrics and criteria to map ecosystems.

Clustering analysis steps for the extra trials

- (1) Identify the cells in the study area under the resolution of 1/20 degree. In total, there are 627,077 cells in study area. All of them were analysed throughout all the trials. The following 11 near seabed layers' cells located in the study area were used in clustering analysis:
 - Bathymetry Depth Mean,
 - Dissolved Molecular Oxygen Benthic Mean Mean2010_2020,
 - Nitrate Benthic Mean Mean2010_2020,
 - Ocean Temperature Benthic Mean Mean2010_2020,
 - pH Benthic Mean Mean2010_2020,
 - Phosphate Benthic Mean Mean2000_2010,
 - Salinity Benthic Mean Mean2010_2020,
 - Slope Benthic Mean,
 - Terrain Ruggedness Index Benthic Mean,
 - Topographic Position Index Benthic Mean,
 - Total Phytoplankton Benthic Mean Mean2010_2020.
- (2) The layers were standardized by the zscore method, centered to have mean 0 and scaled to have standard deviation 1.
- (3) Principal component analysis (PCA) was used to perform dimensionality reduction and exclude correlation among variables. Based on the 11 variables, 6 components (together explain 91% information) were chosen for the following clustering analysis.
- (4) In every clustering analysis: (a) The parameter of “Max Iteration” was set adequately high to ensure every clustering analysis can complete within the max iteration limit; (b) The parameter of “replicate” was set as 10 to select the clustering result which has best mathematic performance from the 10 replicates.
- (5) Evaluating proper clustering methods and then mapping near seabed ecosystems accordingly, details see the next.

Evaluate clustering methods and k numbers

The three methods for assessing the number of clusters (see Table S1, Figure S1a-c) yielded that the best solutions are: k=9 (Figure S2a), k=13 (Figure S2b), and k=18 (Figure S2c).

*Table S1. Summary of additional distance functions and clustering validation metrics. The best clustering solutions are indicated in **bold***

No.	Cluster method	Distance function	Evaluation method (Figure S1a-c)	Mapping figure No.
1	kmeans*	Cosine similarity	Silhouette 9, 13 (Figure S2b) ,18	Fig. S3a, S2b, S3b
2	kmeans	Correlation	Silhouette 9,13, 18	Fig. S4a, S4b, S4c
3	kmeans	sqEuclidean	Silhouette 9 (Figure S2a) ,13, 18	Fig. S2a, S3e, S3f
4	kmeans	Cityblock	Silhouette 9,13, 18	Fig. S4d, S4e, S4f
5	kmeans	sqEuclidean	Calinski-Harabasz 8,13,18	Fig. S2a, S3e, S3f
6	kmeans	sqEuclidean	Davies-Bouldin 6,16,18	Fig. S2a, S3e, S3f
7	gaussian mixture distribution**	Mahalanobis distances, derived from Euclidean D.	Silhouette 9,13, 18 (Figure S2c)	Fig. S3c, S3d, S2c

*For kmeans analysis, the algorithm “k-means++” (Arthur & Vassilvitskii, 2007) is used to choose the initial values (or "seeds"), to avoid kmeans getting trapped in poor local optima.

**Gaussian Mixture Models (GMM) are probabilistic models used for representing normally distributed subpopulations within an overall population. In essence, a GMM assumes that the data are generated from a mixture of several Gaussian distributions, each with its own mean and covariance. It uses the Mahalanobis distance, which accounts for covariance, derived from Euclidean distances between data points and the mean.

Figure S1. Optimal number of clusters according to the evaluation methods of (a) Silhouette (Rousseeuw, 1987); (b) Calinsk-iHarabasz (Caliński & Harabasz, 1974); and (c) Davies-Bouldin (Davies & Bouldin, 1979) Numbers in parentheses indicates the corresponding clustering method combination (see Table S1).

Figure S2. Marine ecosystems of near seabed waters of European seas. Mapping solutions with: (a) 9 clusters by kmeans using Euclidean Distance; (b) 13 clusters by kmeans using cosine similarity; (c) 18 clusters by Gaussian Mixture Models. Different colours represent different ecosystems. For further details see Table S1.

Different mapping results for the marine ecosystems of near seabed waters of European seas.

Figure S3. Marine ecosystems of near seabed waters of European seas. Mapping solutions with: (a) 9 clusters and (b) 18 clusters by kmeans using cosine similarity; (c) 9 clusters and (d) 13 clusters by Gaussian Mixture Models using Mahalanobis distances; (e) 13 clusters and (f) 18 clusters by kmeans using Euclidean Distance. Different colours represent different ecosystems. For further details see Table S1.

Figure S4. Marine ecosystems of near seabed waters of European seas. Mapping solutions with: (a) 9 clusters, (c) 13 clusters and (b) 18 clusters by kmeans using correlation; (d) 9 clusters, (e) 13 clusters and (f) 18 clusters by kmeans using cityblock. Different colours represent different ecosystems. For further details see Table S1.

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